

Have you ever wondered how the next generation of rescuers' life can become easier on the operation field?

first RESponder-Centered support toolkit for operating in adverse and infrastrUcture-less EnviRonments – *“The case of mountain rescue scenario”*

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The Project

RESCUER tools and systems will *enhance the senses* of first responders, *aid the localization* of both themselves and victims, and *improve their situational awareness* through smart processing and AR visualizations.

RESCUER tools focus on the case of *adverse conditions* and/or lack of infrastructure, relying only on hardware carried by the first responders themselves.

The Consortium

20 partners from:

- Spain
- Italy
- France
- Greece
- Germany
- United Kingdom
- Portugal
- Slovakia
- Austria

9 research institutes

6 end-users

3 SMEs

1 large enterprise

1 ICT company

The Goal

RESCUER aims:

- to create and develop a **technology toolkit** with a First Responder focus.
- equip **the upcoming group** of first responders.
- enhancing the **effectiveness** and **safety** of their operations.
- especially **under tough** circumstances.
- **both** in terms of infrastructure and the environment.

“HERO” (enHanced nEw eRa first respOnder) concept, will deliver a toolkit offering:

1. **Sense augmentation**
2. **Precise and infrastructure-less self-positioning**
3. **Cognitive support** and multi-sense AR interfaces
4. **Robust ad-hoc intra-team communications** for both verbal and data exchanges

The Roadmap

Duration: 36 months
(July 2021 – June 2024)

- Three phases
 - Initial development
 - Core development
 - Maturation Phase

Phase I:

- Use Case Tools' Requirements & Scenarios
- Tools' Architecture & Module Specification
- Technology Research
- Preliminary Modules & Tools Development

Phase II:

- Technology Integration
- 1st Version of RESCUER Edge Tools
- Technical Validation, Testing & Optimization
- Usability & Performance Analysis
- 1st Pilots

Phase III:

- Pilot & First Responders Feedback
- Final Versions of RESCUER Edge Tools
- Technical Validation, Testing & Optimization
- Usability & Performance Analysis
- Final Pilots
- First Responder Feedback & Policy Recommendations

The Tools

Three pillars

- Infrastructure based communication
- Ad-hoc communication
- Internal Communication

Pilots overview

➤ Two pilot cycles

- 1st pilot after the 1st version of the tools
- 2nd pilot after the final tool versions

Country	Scenario	1 st PILOT	2 nd PILOT
GERMANY	Earthquake	November 2022	April 2024
FRANCE	Tunnel fire	October 2023	May 2024
SPAIN	Mountain rescue	January 2023	March 2024

➤ Field trials during tool development

- Before pilots for several testings
- Already executed in:
 - Greece
 - Germany
 - Spain
 - France

➤ 1st pilot cycle goal

- Technical verification and validation
- Requirements will be re-targeted to address the end-user needs

➤ 2nd pilot cycle goal

- Refined results and feedback
- Final version of tools

The execution of this phase will be formulated as **policy outcomes and a set of recommendations.**

Initial Pilot planning

Field trial in Greece

- Old mine of Vavdos, Chalkidiki
- 18th of June 2022
- Technical partners and End-users
 - Urban Search & Rescue Department of Hellenic Rescue Team(HRT)
 - Center for Research & Technology Hellas(CERTH)
 - University of West Attica
- Earthquake scenario
 - INSARAG 2020 Guidelines, Volume 2: Preparedness and Response's
- First in-field testing

Trial results

The radar sensing tool

Trial results

The Robust vision tool

Object detection in smoke: without dehazing pre-processing

Object detection in smoke: with dehazing pre-processing

Use case 1: Earthquake

Weeze / Germany

23-27.11.2022

Scenario objective:

- Test and Evaluation of the RESCUER Tools within an **Earthquake Scenario** with **Collapsed and Damaged Buildings** during ASR 2 and ASR 3 Activities.
- Test of the Improvement of the **Safety** of the First Responders as well as the **Efficiency** (Time Saving) within a Realistic Scenario.

Use case 1: Earthquake

Use case 1: Earthquake

Use case 2: Tunnel fire

Modane, France

27-31.03.2023 reported to
20.10.2023

Scenario objective:

Test and Evaluation of
the RESCUER Tools within a
**Tunnel accident and fire
Scenario**

Use case 2: Tunnel fire

Use case 2: Tunnel fire

Use case 3: Mountain rescue

Navacerrada, Spain

23-27.01.2023

Scenario objective:

Test and Evaluation of
the RESCUER Tools within
a **Mountain Rescue Scenario**
with a **Search and Rescue at
the mountains**

1st site of test: Navacerrada Fire Station

- 6 rooms
 - 7 Stages to test different tools
- Rotation system
- 50 minutes per one session

2nd site of test: Valdesqui ski center

- Desnowing Algorithm in day conditions
- Person detection with Helmet (max. distances)
- AR Interfaces with HoloLens
- Test Wi-Fi finder (maximum distances) at snow
- GPS localization
- Bio signals monitoring
- Voice commands, communication

Use case 3: Mountain rescue

Use case 3: Results

3. Was the RESCUER tool usable during testing?	Number	Percent
No	0	0,00%
Yes	49	100,00%
	49	100,00%

Question 5: Was the whole functionality of the RESCUER tool **usable**?

■ No, only parts were usable during the test. ■ Yes

Question 10: How would you rate the **general performance** of RESCUER tool after the testing?

Use case 3: Results

Use case 3: Mountain rescue

Tools in Pilots overview

TOOL	EARTHQUAKE	TUNNEL FIRE	MOUNTAIN
Smart Helmet	Y	Y	Y
Robust Vision	Y	Y	Y
Visual based self-localization	Y	Y	Y
Enhanced hearing	P	P	N
Augmented olfaction	N	Y	N
Radar sensing and remote touching	Y	Y	N
Signs of life detection	N	Y	N
Data sharing orchestration	Y	Y	Y
INERTIO	Y	Y	Y
Galileo assisted localization	N	Y	Y
Biosignals monitoring	Y	Y	Y
Augmented Reality Interfaces	P	Y	Y
Wireless Finder	Y	P	Y
EBBBB	Y	Y	N
WANET	Y	Y	Y
Seamless communication with C2	P	Y	N
C2 Interface (including Mission Recorder)	P	Y	N

➤ Almost **all** RESCUER Tools were Tested within the first round of pilots as Stand-Alone Tools.

➤ The majority tested in the mountain scenario

- Y = Yes
- N = No
- P = Partially

Questions

Should you have any more questions, please
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